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A COMPARATIVES STUDY OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK PRONUNCIATION CHALLENGES FOR UZBEK LEARNERS

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ANNOTATION

This article looks at the challenges which Uzbek learners facing pronouncing challenges while learning English as a second language. Many learners encounter difficulties with vowel and consonant sounds, stress patterns, and intonation. Identifying these challenges is important for improving English pronunciation skills among Uzbek speakers. This research compares the phonetic systems of both different languages, highlights the most common pronunciation difficulties and discovers practical solutions to intensify phonetic accuracy.

Keywords: *phonetics, second language challenges, pronunciation difficulties, phonological transfer, English as a second language, word stress.*

Introduction:

Pronunciation is one of the main aspects of adopting a new foreign language. It is an important ability for learners since it influences both communication and comprehension. For Uzbek speakers learning English, pronunciation can be particularly challenging due to fundamental differences in phonetic systems. English has a greater variety of sounds, as well as different stress and intonation patterns, than Uzbek, which has a relatively simple vowel and consonant system. The aim of this article is to examine the primary pronunciation issues that Uzbek English language

learners encounter and offer workable solutions. Teachers and students can use more efficient language learning strategies if they are aware of these phonetic variations.

Pourhosein Gilakjani(2016) defined pronunciation as the production of English sounds. According to the Paulston & Burder, 1976, pronunciation is the production of a sound system which does not interfere with communication either from the speakers' and listeners' viewpoint.

1. Vowel Difference Between English and Uzbek.

Vowel sounds which English contains are one of the complicated contents for Uzbek learners and not only. "One of the important problems faced by the students learning English is that, each English vowel has more than one pronunciation"(Mohammed AbdALgane andSomia ALi Mohamed Idris(2023)).

Uzbek has only six vowel phonemes: a,o,i,e,u and o' . , in contrast English has 20. This vast difference leads to often misinterpretatoin and mispronunciation.

Short vs long vowels: In English, the length of vowel sound can literally change the word meaning (e.g., sit vs seat), but in Uzbek, vowel length does not impact to the meaning. This means, Uzbek learners frequently struggle to distinguish between words with similar but differently stressed vowels.

Furthermore, English has a central vowel sound which is [ə](schwa),which absolutely does not exist in Uzbek ,which often leads to error pronunciation and making spoken English sound unnatural. In addition, the English language has many diphthongs, [a] (lime), [eɪ] (day), and [oʊ] (go), while it is clear that, Uzbek vowels are more monophthongal. As a result, Uzbek learnerls are likely to pronounce diphthongs as a monophthongs, leading to unnatural speech patterns.

Short Vs. long vowels:

In English, the length of a vowel sound can change the meaning of word (e.g., hit vs heat). However in Uzbek, vowel length does not really effect the meaning. This is

why Uzbek learners find some difficulties to identify between different words with similar pronunciation and stressed vowels.

2. Consonant challenges for Uzbek learners.

For Uzbek people who study English as a second language, consonant pronunciation may cause dramatic challenges since Uzbek does not have certain consonants which English has.

The [θ] and [ð] sounds: These sounds may be seen in the words like **TH**ink and **TH**is, which do not exist in Uzbek. Consequently, learners often replace them with [s] or [d], pronouncing think as “sink” or this as “dis”, which changes the meaning.

The [w] sound: Uzbek does not have an exact [w] sound, leading to confusion between [w] and [v]. This often results in mispronunciations like “vater” instead of water.

Aspiration of plosives: English has aspirated versions of sounds [p], [t], and [k], meaning they are pronounced with a burst of air (e.g., top). In Uzbek, aspiration is not considered phonemic, so learners often pronounce these sounds too softly, making their speech sound less natural.

3. Stress and Intonation Differences

Uzbek and English have different stress and intonation patterns, which affect the natural flow of speech.

Uzbek and English have different stress and intonation patterns, which affect the natural flow of speech. According to Zakhidova and Abdurakhmonova, in Uzbek, stress is “typically fixed and predictable,” often falling on the final syllable of words. This contrasts with English, where stress placement is more variable and can even change a word’s meaning (e.g., record as a noun vs. record as a verb). As a result, English follows a stress-timed rhythm, where stressed syllables occur at regular intervals and unstressed ones are reduced. In contrast, Uzbek is syllable-timed, meaning each syllable is given roughly equal time. This rhythmic difference may

influence how native speakers of each language perceive and produce the sounds of the other, potentially affecting fluency and accent when learning a new language. **Word stress:** In English, the placement of stress within a word can change its meaning (e.g., record (noun) vs. record (verb)). Uzbek learners often struggle with word stress, making their pronunciation sound unnatural, which can cause misinterpretations.

Rising and falling intonation: English uses rising and falling intonation to show questions, statements, and emphasis. Uzbek learners, who are unfamiliar with this interesting system, may speak English with a flatter intonation, making their speech sound monotonous and less natural.

4. Practical Solutions for Overcoming Pronunciation Challenges.

Improving pronunciation, especially in a foreign language, requires targeted training and rapid practice. Here are some effective techniques for Uzbek learners of **English:**

Phonetic training: Learners should study the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) to understand English sounds more accurately. Minimal pair exercises (e.g., ship vs. sheep) can help distinguish similar sounds.

Shadowing technique: By listening to and repeating native speakers' speech, learners with strong dedication can easily learn how to pronounce and even some complicated words.

Tongue placement exercises help learners understand how to position the tongue for difficult sounds (e.g., [θ] and [ð]), which can improve accuracy.

Technology-assisted learning tools such as Duolingo, Elsa Speak, English Pronunciation Tutor, and Forvo can provide feedbacks. Some of them even interact with learners and analyze pronunciation in real-time, which encourages learner.

Conclusion: Pronunciation is a significant challenge for Uzbek learners of English due to differences in sounds (vowels and consonants), stress patterns, and intonation. Comprehending these differences can help learners focus on main problem

areas and adopt effective pronunciation strategies, which helps them sound more natural. Phonetic training, shadowing techniques, and technology-based learning can significantly improve pronunciation skills.

Further research could explore the effectiveness of phonetic instruction in improving spoken English fluency among Uzbek learners. Future studies may also examine how different teaching methodologies impact pronunciation development.

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